

**Special Issue
“EHMA 2023 Abstract Book”**

Guest Editors: Prof. Sandra C. Buttigieg, MD; Prof. Americo Cicchetti; Prof Axel Kaehne; Dr Alexandre Lourenço; Dr Teppo Heikkilä, MD, EMBA; Prof Todorka Kostadinova; Dr Eszter Kovacs; Prof Federico Lega; Prof Ann Mahon; Dr Rui Dang; Nabil Jamshed MSc MBA BBA; Prof Dr Marija Jevtic, MD; Prof Dr Teresa Magalhães; Prof Dr Henk Nies; Prof Mag Dr Manfred Pferzinger; Prof Dr Rui Santana; Dr Federica Morandi; Mr George Valiotis

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About the EHMA Conference

The EHMA Conference is Europe's preeminent conference on health management. Each year it gathers the full healthcare ecosystem, including health managers and leaders, healthcare professionals, researchers, academics, industry representatives, and decision-makers from Europe, and beyond.

The EHMA Conference provides a platform to discuss the latest health management research, tools and evidence from renowned researchers, academics and professionals. It is concerned on translating research into practice. It creates opportunities for dialogue and exchange on solutions to ensure the sustainability and resilience of health systems.

The EHMA 2023 Annual Conference

EHMA 2023 is the 28th edition of our Annual Conference.

This year's conference theme is 'Health management: sustainable solutions for complex systems'. Three years of the COVID pandemic have exposed gaps and vulnerabilities in European health systems, and the immense pressure on the health and care workforce. Sustainable solutions and strategic thinking are needed to drive the transformation of health systems.

EHMA 2023 is structured around five tracks that reflect the holistic practice of health management, and frame the lenses through which contemporary topics are analysed and discussed.

The European Health Management Association

The European Health Management Association (EHMA) strives for excellent health management for a healthy Europe by supporting the spread of knowledge on effective health management practices. Active since 1982, EHMA exists so that Europe's citizens and communities can benefit from quality, safe, value-based care and health systems.

Our focus is on enhancing the capacity and capabilities of health management to deliver high-quality healthcare and support the successful implementation of health policy. Our commitment is on supporting the provision of data and research findings for evidence-based decision-making and monitoring health policies and practices.

EHMA is the only membership organisation in Europe to bring together the full health management ecosystem, including health and hospital managers, healthcare professionals, researchers, academia, policy and decision-makers. We are a recognised and respected amplifier of best practices in the evolution of health management, and we provide an environment where evidence, challenge and experience are valued and complex debates on current topics can take place.

Sustainable solutions of complex environmental concern in management of pharmaceuticals

Dr Milica Paut Kusturica¹, Prof Dr Marija Jevtic^{1,2,3}, Prof Catherine Bouland³

¹*Faculty of Medicine University of Novi Sad, Serbia.* ²*Institute of Public Health of Vojvodina, Serbia.*

³*Université Libre de Bruxelles (ULB), Research centre on Environmental and Occupational Health, School of Public Health, Belgium*

Human pharmaceuticals are listed as emerging contaminants by UNESCO. Their detection and elimination represent the crucial step according to the “2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development” Goal Targets. Pharmaceuticals become an environmental concern when entering the environment which occurs when residues are excreted after consumption or when unused pharmaceuticals are discarded improperly. The vast majority of pharmaceuticals have not been sufficiently explored for their long-term toxic effects, presence, and fate in the environment. However, certain pharmaceutical groups such as beta-blockers, antibiotics, anticancer drugs, and endocrine disruptors have been shown to cause devastating effects on the ecosystem including increased mortality, and impairment of the physiological and reproductive functions of aquatic species.

Considering that pharmaceuticals provide an unquestionable benefit to human health, great care must be taken not to restrict access to those pharmaceuticals that are necessary but to prevent their negative environmental impact. Given that ‘prevention is better than cure’ the priority is avoidance of pharmaceutical waste.

Various policy interventions are recommended across the lifecycle including source-directed, user-orientated, and waste management measures, to prevent the creation of household pharmaceutical waste and to ensure environmentally friendly ways of pharmaceutical household waste disposal. Preventive measures include rational pharmaceutical consumption, prescribing greener drugs, or designing pharmaceuticals that are benign and easily biodegradable, improved disease prevention, personalised medicine, enhanced dimensioning of pack sizes, and marketplaces for redistribution of unused pharmaceuticals.

The next step is to prevent unavoidable waste to reach the environment due to the practice of improper disposal of unused pharmaceuticals from households which represents a global phenomenon. Thus, effective collection schemes and take-back programs with the main purpose to offer an easy method for disposal of pharmaceutical waste represent an important measure to protect the environment.

Given that financial moment plays a significant role in pharmaceutical waste disposal systems, one of the valuable solutions is an implementation of the EPR laws which require that pharmaceutical manufacturers manage their products in all phases of their life cycle, including end-of-life treatment and waste management.

Finally, educating health professionals and the public and partnership between environmental and healthcare scientists are of crucial importance in all phases of the pharmaceuticals’ lifecycle. The heart of all joint efforts should be the “One Health” approach to tackle pharmaceutical waste and enhance human, animal, and environmental health that are strongly interconnected.

Sustainable solutions of complex environmental concerns in management of pharmaceuticals demand among innovative management, public health and one health approach. Also, it is necessary to strengthen responsibility and procedures not only for the health sector/professionals (by strengthening knowledge in environment and health), but also citizens (by strengthening health literacy).